

A State-Of-The-Art Survey on Deep Learning Methods and Applications

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Abstract—The main objective of this paper is to provide a state-of-the-art survey on deep learning methods and applications. It starts with a short introduction to deep learning and its three main types of deep learning approaches including supervised learning, unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning. In the following deep learning is presented along with a review of state-of-the-art methods including feed forward neural networks, recurrent neural networks, convolutional neural networks and their extended variants. Then a brief overview on the application of deep neural networks in various domains of science and industry is given. Finally, conclusions are drawn in the last section.

Deep Learning; Convolutional Neural Network; Recurrent Neural Network; Long Short-Term Memory; Gated Recurrent Unit

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is a subfield of artificial intelligence that deals with building a computer system that learns from data, which has made significant progress and received enormous attention in the research community and industry. Machine learning is applied successfully to a wide range of problems ranging from image recognition, speech recognition, text classification, online advertising, web search, recommendation systems, etc.

Although all these conventional machine learning methods have been successfully applied in science and industry, these methods are struggling with their ability to deal with natural data in their raw form. Since their beginnings, both machine learning and pattern recognition computer systems required careful engineering and domain knowledge in order to design a feature extractor used to transform the raw data into a feature vector, which was used as input in the learning system [1].

Deep learning is a kind of representation learning (hierarchical feature learning), which makes it easier to extract useful information (automated feature engineering) when building classifiers or other predictors [2]. Additionally, deep learning benefits from the presence of a huge amount of data and fast enough computers which make it possible to train large neural networks. By constructing large neural networks and training them with more data, their performance continues to increase [3].

Deep learning has proved to be successful and used for detection or classification by requiring little engineering and less domain expertise, all these thanks to a large amount of available data and advances in computation power. Deep learning methods use simple but non-linear modules that transform the raw input (natural data) into a higher representation level, slightly more abstract level during the training process [1]. Deep learning methods have achieved state-of-the-art results in diverse applications ranging from computer vision, speech recognition, natural language processing, machine translation, online advertising, web search, recommendation systems, etc.

As presented by [1, 4, 5] the history of deep learning can be divided in three development stages. The first stage consists of some of the early examples (NN architectures) including the Convolutional Neural Networks, in which was showed that neurons can be joined to build a Turing machine [6–8]. The second stage includes application of backpropagation algorithm [9–13]. The third stage of development includes solving the training problem for deep neural networks [14, 15], it is also the time when the term “deep learning” was introduced for the first time. From 2012-present, because of the excellent result reached by [16], deep learning has been extensively applied in various domains by research community and practitioners.

Deep learning involves many challenges that the research community must address. The training of deep neural networks is strongly related to the optimization approach, which is the core component in the training of hard and complex learning problems. Generally, optimization of deep neural networks (update of weights and bias) to minimize the parametrized loss function, hyper-parameter tuning, and complex architectures require too much effort to reach high and acceptable performance. To tackle the optimization in deep learning, several optimization methods and algorithms have been developed, from gradient descent, stochastic gradient descent and its inherited variants, high-derivative and derivative-free optimization methods which are extensively used to improve the optimization performance of deep neural networks in complex and large-scale learning problems.

Furthermore, the availability of large volumes of data and advanced computing hardware (such as GPU and parallel and cloud computing) has played a crucial role in enabling the

training of deep neural networks, and the success reached on large-scale and complex learning problems.

In the last 10 years, there is a lot of effort by the research community devoted to the application of deep learning in several domains, and several contests were won by deep learning methods. Some of the most well-known examples of these applications include object recognition, object detection, image segmentation, speech recognition, machine translation, optical character recognition, handwriting recognition, language identification, audio onset detection, text-to-speech synthesis, social signal classification, video classification, and too many other machine learning tasks. In this paper, we have been much more focused on the research work conducted in the last five years in the field of deep learning.

The number of papers published in the last ten years on some of the most well-known computer libraries (such as IEEE, Nature, Springer, Elsevier, and ACM) better shows the latest trends direction and scientific significance of this field. It is obvious that more and more work pay attention to the application of deep learning methods, we have been much more focused in the last five years, there are several published papers related to this topic every year. Therefore, the research trend on this topic is growing and extending each year.

During our research, we have identified some interesting facts, for example, one of them is that the number of papers published by universities and research institution such as the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research (CIFAR), the University of Toronto (Canada), with main majors in the field (led by Geoffrey Hinton), the University of Montreal, Canada (Yoshua Bengio), New York University, USA (Yann LeCun), and Swiss AI Lab IDSIA (Istituto Dalle Molle di Studi sull'Intelligenza Artificiale) (Jürgen Schmidhuber) have provided a valuable contribution in this field. Also, industrial labs in Google, Facebook, Microsoft, Amazon, Baidu, IBM, Apple, and so many others have brought these algorithms to a larger scale and into products.

Another interesting fact is that deep learning and its successful application have also attracted the attention of several scientific disciplines such as computer vision, image recognition, bioinformatics, biomedical applications, physics, chemistry, and other areas. There have already been two excellent review papers introduced by pioneers of the field. One historical survey that compactly summarizes relevant work from the early development of the field [4], and another one is [1], which presents an excellent and comprehensive overview on deep learning and its application. In meantime, there are several other surveys and overview articles that present comprehensively the latest trends in the field of deep learning and its applications [5, 17, 18].

This paper serves as a complementary one to those previously published, at the same time provides a state-of-the-art review on deep learning, by covering methods, and most recent development trends and application of deep learning methods in several areas of science and industry. First, it gives a short overview of deep learning and feature learning (hierarchical feature learning) used to train deep neural networks, and some other useful background notation. Then, state-of-the-art deep learning methods followed by some of the

most successful applications of these methods by the research community and practitioners have been presented. Finally, besides the recent achievements, some future challenges and limitations are briefly discussed.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Deep Learning

Although conventional machine learning algorithms have shown incredibly good results in various fields, they are characterized by several drawbacks including feature engineering, which is an important but time-consuming task that requires engineering skills and domain expertise. Furthermore, they have problem with large and complex data sets and reach a plateau in performance after a considerable amount of data used in training.

Deep learning is a kind of representation learning that makes it easier to extract useful information (automatically feature engineering) when building classifiers or other predictors [2]. Additionally, deep learning benefits from the presence of a huge amount of data and fast enough computers which make it possible to train large neural networks. By constructing large neural networks and training them with more data, their performance continues to increase [3].

The success of deep learning is strongly related to:

- Availability of faster CPU, the advent of GPU, Multi-GPU, Cloud, and HPC.
- Faster network connectivity and better software infrastructure for distributed computing
- Built of new deep learning packages (Cafee, Keras, TensorFlow, Theano, etc.) which have made possible training of large neural networks.

Supervised learning: Also referred to as learning from labeled data is the most widely used approach in machine learning, deep or not, is supervised learning [1]. The deep learning expansion that we are seeing in practical applications is because of it is fantastic at supervised learning tasks [4]. In supervised learning, both input attributes and output classes are given in advance and the aim is to find a function or hypothesis that correlates the input attributes and the output attribute. Both regression and classification are supervised learning methods. In the case of a regression problem, the output variable is continuous (real domain) and its value is determined as a function of inputs. In classification, on the other hand, the output is a class (discrete class or category) from the domain of possible classes [19].

Unsupervised learning: Is different from classification and regression since only inputs (input vector) is given, without the supervising (output) variable.

Reinforcement learning: Is a promising machine learning approach concerned with how an agent learns by continually interacting with an environment. The working principle of RL is as follow, the agent observes the state of the environment, and based on this state/observation takes an action [20].

B. Feature Learning

III. DEEP LEARNING METHODS

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) or simply neural networks (NN) are a prominent class of machine learning models that are loosely inspired by concepts from biological brains. In general, an ANN is a network composed of connected units or nodes called artificial neurons (processing units), which are interconnected to each other by weighted connections. Each neuron has inputs like x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n and their weights w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n , which usually are real numbers, and an overall bias, b . The output of the neuron is a function $f(w * x + b)$ which is also known as activation function (sigmoid, tanh, ReLU) [22, 23].

Many different variants of ANNs have been presented and studied over the years. In general, they can be classified into two major types based on connection type: (i) ANNs whose connections form cycles, which are known as feedback, recursive, or recurrent, neural networks and (ii) ANNs without cycles (acyclic) are known as feedforward neural networks (FNNs).

A. Feedforward Neural Networks

Feedforward neural networks (FNNs) are neural networks where the output from one layer is used as input to the next layer. These types of networks are acyclic, which means there are no cycles in the network. The term “feedforward” refers to the fact that the information is always fed forward, never fed back. However, there are extended models of artificial neural networks in which feedback connections are possible, we refer to such models as recurrent neural networks [21].

Among different types of FNNs, multilayer perceptron (MLP) [24] has been most extensively studied [23].

Figure 1. Multilayer perceptron, which consists of input layer, hidden layers, and output layer [21].

The Figure 2 shows the multilayer perceptron network, which compounds by the input layer (the leftmost layer in this network), and the neurons in the input layer are known as input neurons. The output layer (rightmost layer in this network) contains the output neurons, or in this case, two output neurons. The hidden layer is in the middle, between input and output, and the neurons in this layer are neither inputs nor outputs.

B. Recurrent Neural Networks

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [24] are an extension of conventional FNNs, in which cyclic connection (feedback) is

possible, which makes enable updating the current state based on past states and current input data [18].

RNNs are specifically designed for the tasks that involve sequential inputs such as time series or natural language, which incorporate correlations between data points that are close in the sequence. Like a CNN that is a neural network that is specialized for processing an X value network such as an image, an RNNs is a neural network that specializes in processing an $x(1)$ value sequence $x(t)$ [21].

Figure 2. General structure of RNNs and unfolded in time of computation for three-time steps involved in forwarding computation [1].

RNNs are characterized by several benefits that make them an attractive choice for processing sequential data. They can successfully handle several machine learning tasks, especially when the input and/or outputs are of variable-length. They remember contextual information from past inputs (and future inputs too, in the case of bidirectional RNNs), which allows them to instantiate a wide range of sequence-to-sequence maps. Furthermore, they are robust to localized distortions of the input sequence along the time axis [23].

RNNs have been extensively used in several machine learning tasks especially with sequential data including speech recognition, sequence labeling, generating sequences, sentiment classification, machine translation, image captioning, video activity recognition, DNA sequence analysis etc.

Over the years, several RNNs variants and extensions have been proposed to tackle two main drawbacks of RNNs, vanishing gradient and the capture of longer-range dependencies. The two most used includes its rich LSTM variants [25] and more recently proposed one known as GRUs [26, 27].

1) *Bidirectional recurrent neural networks* (BRNNs) [28] are extended variant of RNNs architecture. While unidirectional RNNs are influenced from the previous inputs to make predictions about the current state, bidirectional RNNs pull in future data to improve the accuracy of it. In other words, the output is influenced from previous inputs (backwards) and future states (forwards) simultaneously.

Figure 3. Bidirectional recurrent neural network (BRNN) shown unfolded in time of the computation for three-time steps, involved in its forward and backward computation [28].

2) *Long short-term memory*: Although RNNs have proven to perform well in several machine learning tasks, they have a problem with capturing long-term dependencies, which is a truly relevant feature when input data is large. Long short-term memory (LSTM) [25] is an RNN architecture specifically designed to handle the problem of long-term dependencies and performs better at storing and accessing information than standard RNNs. Almost all state-of-the-art results based on RNNs have been achieved by LSTM, and thus it has become so popular in deep learning. LSTM architecture, which uses purpose-built memory cells to remember information for long periods is practical, is better at finding and exploiting long-term dependencies in the data, not something they struggle to learn [29]. LSTM has been shown to reach state-of-the-art results in several sequence processing tasks, ranging from speech and handwriting recognition, speech recognition, sentiment classification, video activity recognition, sequence-based prediction of protein localization, etc.

Figure 4. Diagram for Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [5].

3) *Gated recurrent units*: A gated recurrent unit (GRU) [26] was proposed with idea to make each recurrent unit to adaptively capture dependencies of different time scales. On the same time to reduce computational burden caused by additional parameters used in LSTM. In order to do so, the GRU cell integrates the forget gate and input gate as an update gate that can regulate flow of information, without having a separate memory cell [26, 27].

Figure 5. Diagram for gated recurrent units (GRU) [5].

Advantages/disadvantages: one of the main advantages of GRU is that is a simple model and easier to build a larger network, also has faster computation time. On the other hand, LSTM is more powerful and more flexible, and has been historically more proven choice and extensively used by research community and practitioners, so we can surely say that LSTM can be considered as default and the first thing to try.

C. Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) aka. ConvNets [30] are a special type of neural networks specifically designed to deal with data that come in the form of multiple arrays. Authors in [31] presented the first paper on CNN trained by backpropagation to solve the problem of classifying handwritten digits images. During the 1990s, there have been several successful applications of CNNs, and a surprisingly good result were obtained in tasks such as handwritten digit classification and face detection, speech recognition, and document reading. In the last ten years, several improved architectures have been introduced obtaining state-of-the-art results on almost all benchmark data sets. CNNs or some close variants represent a breakthrough in image processing [16], video, speech, and audio [1].

CNNs use a special architecture that is specifically designed to process data that has a known grid-like topology. Examples include time-series data, which can be thought of as 1-D grid for signals and sequences, including language; 2-D for image data (grid of pixels) or audio spectrograms; and 3-D for video or volumetric images. The term convolutional in CNN refers to the fact that the network typically uses a mathematical operation named convolution, which is a specialized kind of linear operation. CNNs are simply neural networks that employ convolution in place of general matrix multiplication in at least one of their layers [21]. CNNs leverage four basic ideas: local connections, shared weights, pooling, and the use of many layers [1].

Figure 6. General structure of CNN and the training process [32].

A typical CNN architecture consists of a small number of relatively complex layers, with each layer having many “stages.” The first few stages are composed of two types of layers: convolutional layers and pooling layers [1]. Although during the last years, several CNNs architectures have been introduced, almost all of them consist of a key set of basic layers such as the convolution layer, the pooling layer, dense layers, and the softmax layer [5].

For a detailed description on CNNs, historical development, and an overview of applications including numerous contests won by CNN, we refer to [1, 4, 5, 17, 33].

1) *The revival of CNN - 2006*: the year 2006 marks a turning paper on the concept of greedy layer-wise pre-training, which revived research interest in deep learning both in academy and industry [14]. Experimental results from this study and other studies showed that both supervised and unsupervised training can initialize a network in a better way than random initialization [17]. One important improvement concerning neural networks was this of using new activation functions such as ReLU and tanh, etc. Another useful improvement regarding the CNNs was the introduction of max-pooling, which showed surprisingly good results by learning invariant features. On the other side, in the late of 2006s, it was also introduced the graphical processing unit (GPU) that accelerated the training of larger neural networks. In 2010, there was another relevant contribution by Stanford, respectively, the introduction of two large databases, one with millions of images belonging to many classes known as ImageNet, and almost the same time they released large data set for object detection named PASCAL 2010 VOC, which have been used as benchmark data set [17].

2) *Rise of CNN - 2012-2014*: the increase in the availability of the annotated data and improvement in the hardware technology are among the key factors that contributed more to swiftly advance research in CNNs achieving state-of-the-art results in numerous tasks. Besides, other relevant elements including parameter optimization algorithms and new architectural ideas have accelerated the research and dramatically improved the performance of CNNs in several tasks ranging from visual object recognition, object detection, speech recognition, and many others [33, 17]. The breakthrough that used deep CNNs was brought by AlexNet [16] that showed outstanding performance in ImageNet

(ILSVRC-2012) by reducing almost halve error rate as compared to conventional computer vision techniques, which precipitated the rapid adoption of deep learning by the computer vision community [1]. Other CNN architectures have been introduced during that time, but we will mention three of them which performed state-of-the-art results in image recognition. ZFNet [34] an extended CNN architecture over AlexNet, which outperformed AlexNet and won the ILSVRC 2013 contest. A year later, it was another CNN architecture known as Visual Geometry Group (VGG) introduced by [35] that won the 2014 ILSVRC, at the same time they showed that VGG generalizes well to other datasets, achieving state-of-the-art results. At the same time with VGG was introduced the GoogLeNet [36], which is a CNN architecture codenamed Inception that achieved the new state-of-the-art for classification and detection in the ImageNet 2014 (ILSVRC2014).

3) *CNN 2015-Present*: During the last years (from 2015-2020), the research work in CNN is still going on, more and more efforts have been devoted by the research community providing significant improvements in CNN performance. In this regard, several extended variants of CNN architecture have been proposed.

a) *Inception-V3* [37] demonstrated substantial gains over the state-of-the-art via to carefully factorized convolutions and aggressive regularization.

b) *Highway network* [38], which is based on the intuition that the learning capacity can be improved by increasing the network depth [17].

c) *Inception-V4 and Inception-ResNet* [39], which is based on the introduction of residual connections with traditional CNN architecture and achieved state-of-the-art performance in the ImageNet 2015 (ILSVRC 2015). ResNet (residual nets) [40] was evaluated in ImageNet dataset with a depth of up to 152 layers, which was 8 times deeper than VGG nets but still having lower complexity. An ensemble of these residual nets achieved a 3.57% error on the ImageNet test set and won 1st place on the ImageNet 2015 (ILSVRC 2015) classification task. ResNet revolutionized the CNN architectural race by introducing the concept of residual learning in CNNs and devised an efficient methodology for the training of deep networks [17].

d) *WideResNet (Wide residual networks)* [41] - in this paper authors conduct a detailed experimental study on the architecture of ResNet blocks, based on which they proposed a novel architecture where they decrease the depth and increase the width of residual networks. They have also demonstrated that even a simple 16-layer-deep wide residual network outperforms in accuracy and efficiency all previous deep residual networks, including thousand-layer-deep networks, achieving new state-of-the-art results on CIFAR, SVHN, COCO, and significant improvements on ImageNet.

e) *DenseNet* [42] - connects each layer to every other layer in a feed-forward fashion. Some of the main advantages of DenseNets are as follows: they alleviate the vanishing

gradient problem, strengthen feature propagation, encourage feature reuse, and substantially reduce the number of parameters. DenseNets obtained significant improvements over the state-of-the-art on most of them, whilst requiring less memory and computation to achieve high performance.

f) *MobileNets* [43] – authors here presented a class of efficient models called MobileNets for mobile and embedded vision applications. They have also demonstrated the effectiveness of MobileNets across a wide range of applications and use cases including object detection, fine-grain classification, face attributes, and large-scale geo-localization.

g) *Xception* [44] – as described by authors here in this paper this architecture, slightly outperforms InceptionV3 on the ImageNet dataset, and significantly outperforms Inception V3 on a larger image classification dataset comprising 350 million images and 17,000 classes. Although the Xception architecture has the same number of parameters as Inception V3, the performance gains are not due to increased capacity but rather to more efficient use of model parameters.

h) *Residual Attention Neural Network* [45] – is a convolutional neural network using attention mechanism which can incorporate with state-of-art feed-forward network architecture in an end-to-end training fashion. This architecture achieved state-of-the-art results in object recognition performance on three benchmark datasets including CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and ImageNet.

i) *ResNeXt* [46] - a simple, highly modularized network architecture for image classification, which was constructed by repeating a building block that aggregates a set of transformations with the same topology. ResNeXt won 2nd place in the ILSVRC 2016 contest, respectively on the classification task. The authors further investigated ResNeXt on an ImageNet-5K set and the COCO detection set, also showing better results than its ResNet counterpart.

j) *SENet* [47] - also known as “Squeeze-and-Excitation” (SE) was one that won 1st place in ILSVRC 2017 classification contest by significantly reducing the top-5 error to 2.251.

k) *Convolutional Block Attention Module (ResNeXt101 (32x4d) + CBAM)* [48] – to verify its efficacy, authors conducted extensive experiments with various state-of-the-art models and confirmed that CBAM outperforms all the baselines on three different benchmark datasets: ImageNet1K, MS COCO, and VOC 2007. They also find out that the overall overhead of CBAM is quite small in terms of both parameters and computation.

l) *Other CNN architectures* - there are some other proposed CNN architectures including FractalNet [49], DelugeNet [50], PolyNet [51], PyramidNet [52], Concurrent Spatial and Channel Excitation Mechanism [53], Channel Boosted CNN [54], Competitive Squeeze and Excitation Network CMPE-SE-WRN-28 [55].

IV. APPLICATION OF DEEP LEARNING METHODS

In this section, we have presented some of the most recent trends in the application of deep learning focusing on the last 5 years. In the first part of this section, we shortly review some practical applications of CNN in image processing and computer vision, speech processing, and medical imaging. In the second part, we bring another overview of the application of RNNs including their rich variants (LSTM and GRU).

A. Applications of CNNs

In recent years, deep CNNs are at the core of most state-of-the-art computer vision solutions for a wide variety of tasks [37]. In other words, this success represents a huge impact in computer vision. CNNs can be surely considered as the dominant approach for almost all recognition tasks by providing human performance for a variety of tasks, namely image recognition, classification, detection, regression, segmentation mainly tested against the ImageNet data set on the ILSVRC (classification and detection challenge) including [37–47, 49–57].

CNNs have also been successfully applied in speech recognition [58–63], face recognition [64–68], predicting drug-target interactions [69–73], analyzing particle physics data [74–76], in bioinformatics predicting on gene expression and disease [77–80], predicting DNA–protein binding [81–88]. Other examples of application of CNN architectures includes audio classification [89–93].

Perhaps more surprisingly, CNN has been successfully applied for several tasks in natural language understanding ranging from text classification [94–99], topic classification [100], sentiment analysis [101–104], question answering [105–107], language modeling [108], image captioning and visual question answering [109], language translation [110–112], sign language recognition [113–116], video classification [117–120], etc.

B. Applications of RNNs

RNNs have been widely and successfully applied in several machine learning tasks dealing with sequential inputs, such as speech and language. However, RNNs compounding by sigma cells or tanh cells is not suitable for capturing long-term dependencies. To tackle this drawback were introduced gate functions into the cell structure which allows long-term dependencies, and one of the most widely and successfully used is LSTM, which is part of almost all the exciting results based on RNNs [18], particularly stacks of LSTM-RNNs and GRU-RNNs.

Some successful application examples of RNNs includes speech recognition [121–126], keyword spotting tasks [127–129], TIMIT phoneme recognition benchmark [130, 131]. Recently, the RNNs have been widely used for the recommender systems and results showed significant improvement over conventional recommendation systems [132–142]. Some other domains where RNNs has been applied are in robotics including application for robot

localization [143], robot-assisted feeding [144], and robot control [145–147].

RNNs has achieved state-of-the-art performance in a variety of NLP tasks such as language modeling [148–151], text-to-speech [152–154], machine translation [155], speaker diarization [156, 157], natural language generation [158, 159], natural language understanding [160, 161], question answering [162, 163], chatbot application [164–166]. More recently, RNNs have achieved state-of-the-art results for speech emotion recognition [167–169], emotion detection [170], and many other tasks.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces and summarizes state-of-the-art deep learning methods, focusing on the two supervised deep learning methods, respectively CNNs and RNNs which have attracted tremendous attention in the last 10 years. Almost all machine learning tasks belong to the supervised learning approach, which is largely based on CNNs and RNNs. Thus, this is the reason that these two methods play a major role in deep learning. Firstly, we describe the background theory of deep learning and feature learning, then, supervised deep learning methods such as FNNs (MLP), CNNs, and their extended variants/architectures, following RNNs and their rich variants (LSTM, GRU, and BRNN). Then we describe the applications of the deep learning methods in several domains including machine learning, computer vision, and NLP.

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